

IN SILICO IDENTIFICATION OF CANDIDATE GENES FOR DEHYDRATION STRESS RESPONSE IN ROBUSTA COFFEE GENOME (*COFFEA CANEPHORA* L.)

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Received Date: 16/11/2022; Revised Date: 04/12/2022; Accepted for Publication: 05/12/2022

SUMMARY

Coffea canephora L., which is belonging to the Rubiaceae family, is one of the most popular cultivated coffee worldwide. In this study, we identified and analysed candidate genes that involve in dehydration stresses response in *C. canephora* L. genome. The results showed that genome of *C. canephora* L. consists of 37 protein-coding genes related to drought stress response which are divided into 5 main groups depending on domain and motif such as Dehydration-induced 19 (Di 19); Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related genes; Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein; Dehydration-responsive protein RD22; Early responsive dehydration (ERD). Determination of subcellular localization indicated that there are 2 protein-coding genes as Cc01_g21190 and Cc08_g08870 localize in chloroplast; 1 protein-coding gene as Cc10_g02270 localize in mitochondria and 1 protein coding gene as Cc05_g03850 localize in peroxisome. The study on candidate protein coding genes relating dehydration stress response is important for elucidating protein functions involved in various cellular processes and stress response.

Keywords: *C. canephora* L., genome, ERD, in silico, localization, stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

C. canephora L. and *C. arabica* are most coffee bean productions (ICO, 2021) with 30% and 70% in total production worldwide, respectively. ICO (2021) was estimated that an average of 2.25 billion cups of coffee are consumed around the world, bringing approximately 12 billion US dollars in income each year. *C. canephora* L. contents higher caffeine and bitter taste than *C. arabica*.

In the last two decades, several articles were published about genome sequencing, coffee transcriptomes, and expressed sequence tags (ESTs) for both robusta and arabica coffee plants (Pallavicini et al., 2005) (Esteves Vieira et al., 2006). An oligo-based microarray containing 15,721 coffee genes was constructed to analyze potential genes involved in bean maturation, pathogen resistance, and stress responses (Privat et al., 2011). EST sequences of *C. arabica* were recently released (Mishra and Slater, 2012). Especially, Denoeud et al., 2014 reported that *C. canephora* genome contains 25,574 protein-coding genes, 2,573 organellar-to-nuclear genome transfers, 6,812 predicted transposable elements (TEs), and 92 microRNA precursors which were published on Coffee Genome Hub (<http://coffee-genome.org>).

3-caffeoylquinic acid (chlorogenic acid) and

caffeine contents are the most important secondary metabolites of coffee, determining the taste and aroma. It has been reported that there is a strong link between drought conditions and the caffeine as well as chlorogenic acid content of coffee. (Catarino et al., 2021) have mentioned that drought effects increase leaf 5-o-caffeoylquinic acid and caffeine concentrations during the early growth of *Coffea arabica* plants. The understanding of acclimation strategies to climate changes is decisive to ensure coffee crop sustainability, since these environmental conditions determine the suitability of cultivation areas. Thus, identifying the genes in drought conditions associated with the caffeine biosynthetic pathway in coffee provided the molecular tool help coffee breeding and possibly produce more caffeine contents and caffeine-free coffee for consumers in the future. Some molecular functions of coffee genes related to caffeine biosynthesis were reported. McCarthy et al. (McCarthy et al., 2007) have analyzed XMT and DXMT N-methyltransferases from *C. canephora*. Denoeud et al. (2014) analyzed information on the convergent evolution of caffeine biosynthesis by some genes such as CcXMT, CcMXMT, CcMTL, CcDXMT, etc. Perrois et al. (2015) demonstrated that differential regulation of caffeine metabolism depends on the transcriptional activity that controls differential

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expression of XMT1 and DXMT genes in *C. arabica* and *C. canephora*. Recently, Raharimalala et al. (2021) showed very interesting results that *Coffea humblotiana*, a wild species of the Comoro archipelago, lacks a caffeine synthase-encoding gene involved in the naturally decaffeinated status. Up to now, the evolution of the NMT genes in *C. canephora* is NMT2: cc02_g09350; DXMT: cc01_g00720; XMT: cc09_g06970; MXMT: cc00_g24720; NMT3: cc09_g06960; MTL: cc09_g06950), which represent the methylation steps of caffeine biosynthesis.

Moreover, molecular functions of some coffee genes related to biotic and abiotic response genes were also published. Metallothioneine gene expression studies, including CaMT4, CaMT15, CaMT3 and CaMT8 was to elucidate the role of metallothioneine in maintaining Cu and Zn homeostasis and in detoxifying these excess nutrients (Bulgarelli et al., 2016). The full-length *C. arabica* Protein Domain (CaBDP) gene sequence was extracted from the RNA of drought-tolerant *C. arabica* leaves. Genes have been cloned in *Arabidopsis* to characterize plant drought and salt tolerance (Nguyen Dinh et al., 2016; Dinh and Kang, 2017). Torres et al. (2019) indicated that DREB-like gene plays a role for abiotic stress regulators as cold, heat, low relative humidity, high abscisic acid and light stresses in *C. arabica* and water deficit in *C. canephora*.

A number of genes for tolerance to biological stresses in coffee have recently been discovered. CaWRKY1 gene in *C. arabica* is a positive control against Rust fungus *Hemileia vastatrix*. α -amylase inhibitor-1 gene (α -AI1) was able to protect from coffee berry borer insect-pest by *Hypothenemus hampei* for coffee plants (Barbosa et al., 2010; Albuquerque et al., 2015). CaNPR1 gene plays an important role in resistance against coffee leaf rust caused by *H. growatrix* in *C. arabica* and other plants (Vadivelu, 2013), and its role in tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses was demonstrated in many crops (Silva et al., 2018). Nguyen Dinh Sy et al., 2022 overview *C. canephora* L. genome and its function in stress response and caffeine biosynthesis.

There are many genes, activators, and promoter genes in coffee plants which are continuously being discovered to elucidate their function, especially in an adverse environment. Therefore, this research wants to screen and analyze dehydration-related gene of coffee genome that select candidate gene for transgenic coffee plants to overcome drought stresses.

2. CONTENTS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

- DNA sequencing genome of *C. canephora* that downloaded from website Coffee Genome Hub (coffee-genome.org/coffeacanephora).

2.2. Contents

- Screening and identification of dehydration response genes.

- Phylogenetic tree reconstruction

- Protein analysis (motif; domain and subcellular localization).

2.3. Methods

- Screening and identification of dehydration response genes: The predicted name of total 25,574 protein-coding genes in *C. canephora* genome obtained from <http://coffee-genome.org> were downloaded and saved as a word file. Using the key words such as “Dehydration”, “Heat stress”, “Drought stress” to find word, text or other content in the file, all marching gen name is isolated as the genes related to dehydration response.

- Phylogenetic tree reconstruction: Total 37 dehydration related protein sequences were aligned by CLUSTALW. Consequently, phylogenetic tree reconstructions were performed using the function "build" of ETE3 3.1.2 (Huerta-Cepas et al., 2016) as implemented on the GenomeNet (<https://www.genome.jp/tools/ete/>). User provided the multiple sequence alignment. The tree was constructed using FastTree v2.1.8 with default parameters (Price et al., 2010).

- Protein analysis (motif; domain and subcellular localization):

Protein sequences of 37 genes were imported in Wolf PSORT (<https://wolfsort.hgc.jp/>) to predict subcellular localization.

Protein sequence of each gene in total 37 genes were put on software SMART (<http://smart.embl.de>) to analyze domain and motif structure.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Identification and classification of dehydration-related genes

From a total of 25.574 genes in coffee genome (Denoeud et al., 2014), screening on protein-coding genes for dehydration showed that there are total 37 genes which anchored regularly in 10 chromosomes (chro.), except chro. 4 (table 1, figure 1). In detail, there are 2 genes in each chro. 3 (Cc03_g01240; Cc03_g01250), chro. 5 (Cc05_g03450; Cc05_g03850), chro. 7 (Cc07_g10980; Cc07_g11260), chro. 9 (Cc09_g01310; Cc09_g03140),

chro. 10 (Cc10_g02270; Cc10_g07790), chro. 11 (Cc11_g12570; Cc11_g15200); chro. 1 and chro. 6 contains 3 genes (Cc01_g09680; Cc01_g19760; Cc01_g19760) and (Cc06_g10260; Cc06_g10450; Cc06_g16660), respectively; chro. 2 contains 5 genes (Cc02_g03430; Cc02_g05970; Cc02_g13730; Cc02_g30360; Cc02_g30370; Cc02_g34590); chro. 8 contains 9 genes (Cc08_g04040; Cc08_g04050; Cc08_g08440; Cc08_g08450; Cc08_g08460; Cc08_g08470; Cc08_g08860; Cc08_g08870; Cc08_g09520; Cc08_g13960). The length of dehydration related genes is from 387 to 3690 nucleotides

Table 1. The list of protein-coding genes that related to Dehydration/Senescence response in *C. canephora* genome

Gene	Protein-coding gene	No. nu	No. aa.
Cc01_g09680	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 1C	903	301
Cc01_g19760	ERD (early-responsive to dehydration stress) family protein	2271	757
Cc01_g21190	Putative Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19 homolog 3	390	130
Cc02_g03430	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 1D	702	234
Cc02_g05970	Putative Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 2C	1068	356
Cc02_g13730	Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19	726	242
Cc02_g30360	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	510	170
Cc02_g30370	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	2142	714
Cc02_g34590	Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19 homolog 3	366	122
Cc03_g01240	Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19 homolog 3	318	106
Cc03_g01250	Putative Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19 homolog 7	420	140
Cc05_g03450	ERD (early-responsive to dehydration stress) family protein	2334	778
Cc05_g03850	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 2G, putative	582	194
Cc06_g10260	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 3	984	328
Cc06_g10450	Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related	1128	376
Cc06_g16660	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 2F	861	287
Cc07_g10980	Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related	1359	453
Cc07_g11260	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	2448	816
Cc08_g04040	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	2397	799
Cc08_g04050	ERD (early-responsive to dehydration stress) family protein	2628	876
Cc08_g08440	Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	618	206
Cc08_g08450	Putative Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	939	313
Cc08_g08460	Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	1014	338
Cc08_g08470	Putative Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	1110	370
Cc08_g08860	Putative Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	927	309
Cc08_g08870	Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	387	129
Cc08_g09520	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 3	846	282
Cc08_g13960	Putative Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 1D	780	260
Cc09_g01310	ERD (early-responsive to dehydration stress) family protein	2307	769
Cc09_g03140	Putative Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 2D	693	231
Cc10_g02270	Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 2G, putative	774	257
Cc10_g07790	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	2238	746

Gene	Protein-coding gene	No. nu	No. aa.
Cc11_g12570	Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD4)	2145	715
Cc11_g15200	Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related	1337	459
Cc00_g24050	Putative Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	927	309
Cc00_g26390	Putative Protein DEHYDRATION-INDUCED 19 homolog 5	645	215
Cc00_g29410	Putative Dehydration-responsive protein RD22	993	331

Figure 1. The locations of dehydration response genes on 11 chromosomes of Robusta coffee genome (*C. canephora*)

3.2. Phylogenetic tree reconstructions

Protein sequences of 37 genes were analyzed by using phylogenetic tree reconstructions that were performed using software on GenomeNet (<https://www.genome.jp/tools/ete/>) in order to understand the similarity of structure in motif and domain. The result revealed five major groups of

dehydration protein involving Early Responsive Dehydration (ERD); Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related; Dehydration-induced 19; Dehydration-responsive protein RD22; Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree showing the five identified groups within a total of 37 proteins relating to dehydration response

3.3. Motif and domain structure

SMART software (<http://smart.embl.de>) was applied to analyze domain and motif protein structure of five groups: Early Responsive Dehydration (ERD); Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related; Dehydration-induced 19; Dehydration-responsive protein RD22; Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein.

Group 1: Early-responsive to dehydration stress protein (ERD)

ERD group includes 10 protein-coding genes which contain RSN1 and PHM7 domain (Figure 3). RSN1 domain was found in eukaryotic transmembrane proteins that are involved

in diverse functions, including phosphate metabolism (Ogawa, DeRisi and Brown, 2000) and spore wall assembly (Coluccio et al., 2004), which represents the seven transmembrane domain regions of phosphate transporters (Zhu et al., 2008). PHM7 is the predicted cytosolic domain of integral membrane proteins, which usually precedes the 7TM region and follows a RSN1_TM. This domain is distantly homologous RRM clan for RNA binding proteins (Zhu et al., 2008). Moreover, some proteins contain transmembrane helix region.

Figure 3. Motif and domain structure of early-responsive to dehydration stress group (ERD)

Blue: transmembrane helix region; Pink: low complexity region

Group 2: Senescence/dehydration-associated proteins

There are three protein-coding genes containing senescence domain that senescence proteins produced around that time have a role in this program (Panavas et al., 1999).

Figure 4. Motif and domain structure of Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related group

Pink: low complexity region

Group 3: Protein dehydration-induced 19

The C-terminal domain of protein dehydration-induced 19 (Di19) is a protein that increases the sensitivity of plants to environmental stress, such as salinity, drought, osmotic stress and cold. It is also induced by an increased supply of stress-related hormones as abscisic acid and ethylene (Li et al., 2010). Moreover, dehydration-induced 19 protein has a zinc-finger at the N terminus (Znf-Di19) which has been found to be strongly expressed in both the roots and leaves of Arabidopsis thaliana during progressive drought (Gosti et al., 1995).

Figure 5. Motif and domain structure of dehydration-induced 19 group (Di 19)

Red: signal peptide; Pink: low complexity region

Group 4: Dehydration-responsive protein RD 22

The BURP domain was abbreviated of BNM2, USP, RD22, and PG1beta depending on the proteins was first identified. The BURP domain-containing proteins consists of three or four modules: (i) an N-terminal hydrophobic domain; (ii) a short conserved segment; (iii) repeated units that is unique to each member; and (iv) the C-terminal BURP domain. This conserved BURP domain presents in diverse plant proteins suggesting that it play an important and fundamental role for plant (Hattori et al., 1998). BURP domain contain a general motif to for localize within the cell wall matrix. The other structural domains associated with the BURP domain may specify for intermolecular interactions (Batchelor et al., 2002).

Figure 6. Motif and domain structure of dehydration-responsive protein RD22

Red: signal peptide; Pink: low complexity region

Group 5: Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein(s)

Dehydration-responsive element-binding proteins contain AP2 domain such as APETALA2 and

EREBPs. The Ethylene-Responsive Element (ERE) is a cis-regulatory element, which identified a short motif rich in G/C nucleotides, the GCC-box, essential for the response to ethylene (Broglie et al., 1989). This short motif is recognized by a family of transcriptional factors, the ERE binding factors (ERF) (Fujimoto et al., 2000) that contain a domain of around 60 amino acids which is also found in the APETALA2 (AP2) protein (Weigel, 1995).

Figure 7. Motif and domain structure of Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein 1C

Pink: low complexity region.

3.4. Predicted protein subcellular localization

Using WoLF PSORT (<https://wolfpsort.hgc.jp/>) to predict subcellular localization of dehydration stress response genes in Robusta coffee genome in the cell such as nucleus (nucl), chloroplast (chlo), mitochondria (mito), cytoplasm (cyto), endoplasmic reticulum (E.R.), plasma membrane (plas), golgi vesicles (golg), vacuole (vacu), peroxysome (pero), etc. Among them, the protein-coding genes presumably located on chloroplast, mitochondria and peroxisome are considered as targeted candidate genes due to its key roles in biotic and abiotic stress response regulation. The result indicated that protein-coding genes as Cc01_g21190 (chlo: 10); Cc08_g08870 (chlo: 9); mitochondria as Cc10_g02270 (mito: 11); peroxisome as Cc05_g03850 (pero: 10). The subcellular localization prediction of total 37 proteins is showed detail in table 2.

Table 2. Predicted subcellular localization of 37 protein-coding genes

Gene name	Protein subcellular localization prediction
Cc01_g09680	nucl:8, chlo:3, cyto:1, mito:1, extr:1
Cc01_g19760	plas:13, E.R.:1
Cc01_g21190	chlo:10, cyto:2, extr:2
Cc02_g03430	nucl:13, cyto:1
Cc02_g05970	nucl:12, chlo:2
Cc02_g13730	nucl:12, cyto:2
Cc02_g30360	plas:4.5, golg:3, cyto_plas:3, vacu:2, E.R.:2, mito:1, extr:1
Cc02_g30370	plas:9, vacu:3, E.R.:1, golg:1
Cc02_g34590	nucl:8.5, cyto_nucl:5, chlo:4, plas:1
Cc03_g01240	cyto:6, chlo:3, extr:2, nucl:1, mito:1, golg:1
Cc03_g01250	chlo:7, nucl:3, extr:3, plas:1
Cc05_g03450	plas:12, E.R.:2
Cc05_g03850	pero:10, cyto:3, nucl:1
Cc06_g10260	nucl: 14
Cc06_g10450	nucl: 6, chlo: 4, mito: 3, cysk: 1
Cc06_g16660	nucl: 12, plas: 1.5, golg_plas: 1.5
Cc07_g10980	chlo: 5, cyto: 4, pero: 3, mito: 2

Gene name	Protein subcellular localization prediction
Cc07_g11260	plas: 11, E.R.: 2, vacu: 1
Cc08_g04040	plas: 12, chlo: 1, E.R.: 1
Cc08_g04050	plas: 10, E.R.: 2, chlo: 1, nucl: 1
Cc08_g08440	cyto: 8, chlo: 5, extr: 1
Cc08_g08450	extr: 10, cyto: 2, chlo: 1, E.R.: 1
Cc08_g08460	extr: 8, vacu: 2, E.R.: 2, chlo: 1, cyto:1
Cc08_g08470	extr: 6, vacu: 4, cyto: 2, chlo: 1, E.R.:1
Cc08_g08860	extr: 7, E.R.: 3, cyto: 2, chlo: 1, mito:1
Cc08_g08870	chlo: 9, cyto: 4, mito: 1
Cc08_g09520	nucl: 11, cyto: 1, cysk: 1, golg: 1
Cc08_g13960	nucl: 14
Cc09_g01310	plas: 13, E.R.: 1
Cc09_g03140	nucl: 11, cyto: 2, plas: 1
Cc10_g02270	mito: 11, nucl: 2, plas: 1
Cc10_g07790	plas: 8, vacu: 3, E.R.: 2, golg: 1
Cc11_g12570	plas: 11, vacu: 1, E.R.: 1, golg: 1
Cc11_g15200	cyto: 6, chlo: 3, mito: 3, nucl: 1, plas:1
Cc00_g24050	cyto: 14
Cc00_g26390	nucl: 14
Cc00_g29410	E.R.:5.5, cyto:5, E.R._plas:3.5, chlo:1, nucl:1, mito:1

4. CONCLUSION

C. canephora L. genome consists of 37 protein-coding genes related to dehydration stress response which are divided into 5 main groups depending on domain and motif such as Dehydration-induced 19; Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related; Dehydration-responsive element-binding

protein; Dehydration-responsive protein RD22; Early Responsive Dehydration-ERD.

Cc01_g21190 and Cc08_g08870 are predicted for chloroplast localization, while Cc05_g03850 and Cc10_g0227 are predicted for peroxisome and mitochondria localization, respectively.

**PHÂN TÍCH NHỮNG GEN ỨNG VIÊN LIÊN QUAN ĐẾN KHẢ NĂNG ĐÁP ỨNG
STRESS HẠN TRONG BỘ GEN CÀ PHÊ VỎI (COFFEA CANEPHORA L.)
BẰNG KỸ THUẬT IN SILICO**

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Ngày nhận bài: 16/11/2022; Ngày phản biện thông qua: 04/12/2022; Ngày duyệt đăng: 05/12/2022

TÓM TẮT

Cà phê vối (*Coffea canephora* L.) thuộc họ Rubiaceae, là một trong 02 loài cà phê được trồng nhiều nhất trên thế giới. Trong nghiên cứu này, chúng tôi sàng lọc và phân tích những gen ứng viên có liên quan đến đáp ứng trong điều kiện khô hạn. Kết quả thu được cho thấy trong bộ gen của *C. canephora* có chứa 37 gen mã hóa protein có khả năng đáp ứng với điều kiện stress khô hạn. Dựa vào phân tích cấu trúc domain và motif, và căn cứ vào cây phả hệ thì chúng được chia thành 05 nhóm chính: nhóm protein cảm ứng (Dehydration induced 19-Di 19); Nhóm protein liên kết (Senescence/dehydration-associated protein-related); Nhóm protein gắn với các nhân tố đáp ứng (Dehydration-responsive element-binding protein); Nhóm protein đáp ứng (Dehydration-responsive protein RD22); và nhóm protein đáp ứng sớm (Early responsive dehydration-ERD). Phân tích dự đoán vị trí protein có thể định vị trong các bào quan của tế bào cho thấy có 2 gen mã hóa protein được dự đoán sẽ định vị trong lục lạp là Cc01_g21190 và Cc08_g08870, trong khi gen Cc10_g02270 mã hóa protein sẽ định vị trong ti thể và gene Cc05_g03850 mã hóa protein sẽ định vị tại peroxisome. Kết quả từ nghiên cứu này sẽ tạo nguồn dữ liệu tin cậy nhằm giúp các nhà khoa học định hướng chọn lựa những gen ứng viên tiềm năng nhất để nghiên cứu sâu chức năng của gen, từ đó ứng dụng vào chọn và tạo giống cà phê có khả năng kháng hạn tốt trong tương lai.

Từ khóa: Bộ gen, *C. canephora*, định vị, ERD, in silico, stress.

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